

SWINOSTICS

Swine diseases field diagnostics toolbox

Newsletter N° 4 - October 2020

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SWINOSTICS news:

✓ *MREs and surface characterization*

In this period, CNR unit with the aim to verify the cross-reactivity between the different target viruses (table 1) has characterized the antibodies by sandwich ELISA test. The MREs immobilization process, on the PIC surface, was evaluated by chemiluminescence and fluorescence methods. The results are shown in **Figure 1**.

Virus	Sample	Cross-reactivity of polyclonal antibodies				
		Anti-PCV2	Anti-PPV	Anti-PRRSV	Anti-CSFV	Anti-ASFV
PCV2	S	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
	P	✓	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
PRRSV	S	(-)	(-)	✓	(-)	(-)
	P	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
PPV	S	(-)	✓	✓	(-)	(-)
	P	(-)	✓	✓	(-)	(-)
ASFV	S	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	✓
	P	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	✓
CSFV	S	(-)	(-)	✓	(-)	(-)
	P	(-)	(-)	✓	✓	✓

Table 1. Cross-reactivity experiment results.

Fig. 1 Results of the chemiluminescence and fluorescence analysis

✓ *PIC preparation for Fiber & microfluidics attachment*

The SWINOSTICS photonic integrated circuit (PIC) was integrated with the microfluidic module and then attached to the optical fiber. **Figure 2** shows the PIC surface integrated into the microfluidic module and **Figure 3** optical fiber was attached to the microfluidic module.

Fig. 2 PIC integrated in the microfluidic module.

Fig. 3 Fiber attached to the microfluidic.

SWINOSTICS news

✓ Mid-project integration week:

9th-13th December 2019, an integration week was organized in CyRIC headquarters. The first version of Swinostics prototype was successfully tested during the integration week (Figure 4 and 5).

Fig. 4 First laboratory prototype at CyRIC laboratories in Cyprus.

Fig. 5 PPV functionalized ring photodiode response.

✓ Full system integration and Laboratory testing using *ref.* samples

CyRIC and ISS developed an updated and compact prototype of the SWINOSTICS device. All system components were included in a robust metal casing. The optimized firmware gives to the user the ability to start the analysis when the device is ready. Fully-integrated prototype of the SWINOSTICS device was tested using reference samples to obtain preliminary data for the performance of the device (sensitivity, specificity & LOD) (**Figure 6 and 7**).

Fig. 6 First integrated SWINOSTICS prototype.

Fig. 7 SWINOSTICS referenced measurements.

Meetings

✓ M24 Project meeting in Budapest

On the 27th and 28th November 2019 the **SWINOSTICS 24M Meeting** was hosted by UVMB in Budapest (Hungary). All partners attended the event. During the meeting, the following issues have been discussed:

- ✓ MREs characterization and surface characterization
- ✓ Functionalization and control of the PIC Surface with the selected MREs
- ✓ PIC preparation for ~~Fiber~~ and microfluidics attachment
- ✓ Virus photonic measurements
- ✓ SWINOSTICS App and Cloud software
- ✓ Dissemination and communication activity

Main Technical Deliverables M24-M36

- D5.2** Preliminary Lab testing prototypes
- D5.3** Preliminary Lab testing prototypes output report
- D5.4** Field testing prototypes
- D7.1** Dissemination and communication plan (UPDATE)
- D7.3** (Preliminary version of) Business plan
- D7.4** (Update of) Standardisation requirements, compliance to methodologies and interaction with working groups report

Fig.8 M24 meeting

✓ M30 Project remote meeting

On the 13th May 2020 the **SWINOSTICS 30M Meeting** meeting organized by CyRIC took place remotely, due to the COVID-19. All partners attended the event. During the meeting, the following issues have been discussed:

- ✓ MREs final experiments and delivery for the PIC assembly
- ✓ PIC assembly and delivery to all pilots
- ✓ First Swinostics prototype assembly
- ✓ Prototype ~~parallelization~~ for all pilot
- ✓ SWINOSTICS App and Cloud software optimization
- ✓ Dissemination and communication activity

30M Meeting SWINOSTICS Project
13th May 2020 – Remote meeting

AGENDA
Wednesday, 13 May 2020

Fig 9. 30M meeting agenda

✓ 2nd Review Meeting

The second SWINOSTICS Review Meeting took place in remote on the 14th of July 2020. The Project Officer and the Reviewers provided valuable comments for improving the system and keeping on track for a future Swinostics-based product.

✓ Planned events:

The next SWINOSTICS Consortium Meeting (M36) probably due to Covid19 emergency will be ~~on~~ remote.

Dissemination Activities

✓ Conferences and Dissemination

New project press release and leaflet were realized during this period and were disseminated in electronic format through the project website and social-media channels of the project

SWINOSTICS at North American PRRS/NC-229 Symposium on PRRS, Emerging and Foreign Diseases of Swine - 1st-2nd November 2019 Chicago (USA).

✓ SWINOSTICS Project Papers

K49, UNIFI and AUA has published a peer-review papers on the Open Access Journal of Veterinary Research

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Point-of-service diagnostic technology for detection of swine viral diseases

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✓ Next events

~~SWINOSTICS final workshops place on the 29th of October 2021.~~

SWINOSTICS Consortium

